

TEACHING IN PRIMARY CLASSES BASED ON AN INNOVATIVE APPROACH THE UNIQUENESS OF THE ORGANIZATION

Ziyodullayeva E'zoza Kamoliddin qizi
Termiz State Pedagogical Institute
Primary education 2nd year student

Abstract: *This article is about organizing effective lessons in elementary grades, informing students about innovation and innovative approach, introducing new things to lessons, making the lesson unique, interesting and understandable, and about the teacher's innovative approach to this stated.*

Key words: *Innovation, principle, primary school students, school, pedagogue, innovative approach, modern schools, traditional education, modern education, method.*

Since primary education is the main link of general education schools, it is necessary to pay more attention to the perfect development of the student's personality in this process. Here, of course, primary school teachers have unlimited responsibilities. They accustom the students who have just stepped on the threshold of the school to the school life and pave the way for them to receive modern education. It is during this period that children's attitudes towards learning and their intellectual potential are formed. This also shows that the task of primary school teachers is responsible. Primary school teachers should conduct lessons based on innovative approaches. The innovative educational system is a rapidly developing knowledge system that has attracted the attention of specialists in all aspects of the educational field. The pedagogues, realizing its educational importance, organize education using advanced innovations in traditional education. The main task of this new form of education, which is currently developing, is to reorganize and master

the prevailing theory of the entire educational system based on innovation. Innovation, idea, tool (new method) can be taken as the main concepts of innovation.

Innovation - (English "Innovation" - introduction of new) - changing the internal structure of the system, an important part of practice and theory. Pedagogical innovation is a means of enriching and developing the theoretical and practical aspect of education and training by introducing previously unknown changes in the educational process. It is clear from this that the innovation process is the introduction of innovation and conditions, a change that ensures the successful transition of the system to new indicators. Therefore, innovation is the process of preparing for innovative changes and putting them into practice. The most important and central issue of the teacher's innovative activity is the quality and efficient organization of the educational process. This activity does not only concern the teacher personally, but can also be at a number of individual, group, public, and institutional levels. The teaching process includes the activities of the teacher and students. The activity of the teacher is to explain the educational material, increase students' interest in science, deepen their thinking and form their beliefs, guide students' independent activities, check and evaluate their knowledge, skills and abilities. A teacher who is passionate about his work has real passion. It is of great importance to develop students' motivation to study in the process of primary school education. Because the motive makes students interested in the educational process, encourages them to actively participate in classes and acquire knowledge. Innovative technologies greatly help to develop the motivation to study. It should not be forgotten that it is necessary to take into account the age and level of knowledge of more children in primary classes. Teaching them using simple, easy, and time-saving play exercises will work well. Activities connected more with the environment develop children's mind, outlook, free thinking, expressive ability, and independent work skills. The peculiarity of using innovative technologies in the course of the lesson is that they are implemented through the joint activities of teachers and

students. There are didactic principles of innovative technologies that can be used in primary classes.

Didactic principles of innovative technologies:

The principle of scientificity - the teaching material of any educational subject showed that science should rely on modern achievements. This principle is implemented in the creation of training programs, training manuals, textbooks. According to the scientific principle, it is necessary to improve the working curricula of subjects and educational materials every year.

The design principle is the organization of the educational process, the document educational process graph, the curriculum, the working curriculum of the subject, the categories of educational goals of the subject departments, the criteria for evaluating the acquired knowledge and skills, the technology of the educational process means to create.

The principle of systematicity - all elements of the educational process are designed as a single system based on the condition of their interdependence.

The principle of goal-orientation - the teaching process of each subject should be aimed at a certain goal.

The principle of controllability - the planned result of training can be achieved if the learning process is controlled.

The principle of repetition - in modern production conditions, the production of the required amount of products is carried out on the basis of pre-prepared documents.

The principle of effectiveness - indicates the possibility of guaranteed achievement of the intended results of teaching innovative technologies with acceptable documents.

The principle of humanization and humanization of the educational process.

The principle of continuity of education.

The principle of activity approach - the current stage of scientific and technical development is characterized by the use of complex high technologies, the production of products requiring science.

Despite the fact that students receive news and have different tendencies and temperaments, the teacher should teach students to think independently, observe, and draw conclusions. In this, the student is the main driving force, and can read, read, draw, understand the formulas of projections and use tools, be friendly with each other, and help each other in solving the problems set before them. giving is their main task. Changes and realizations taking place in the educational system, along with giving students new knowledge, skills and qualifications, inculcate the patriotic ideas of change in relation to society, the state, nature, and other people. he also intends to instill it in his heart. This is especially important for elementary school students. Innovative, interactive education allows the teacher and the student to constantly search for creativity, continuously develop and improve their personality. The teacher is not only trained, but also taught to learn, work and learn independently. Students are taught to learn through independent analysis, to think creatively, to think freely based on personal conclusions, to think freely based on personal conclusions. The student is not given ready-made knowledge, but an opportunity is created for creative observation by searching, finding and processing knowledge from textbooks, information-resource centers, the Internet and various other sources. The student is taught to work with textbooks, read, study, write a synopsis, acquire the skills of independent learning using additional literature and resources. All students in the class are guaranteed to master at the level of their abilities.

Conclusion: In conclusion, we must say that in the era of the development of the information and communication system, it is very important for a teacher of primary education to know techniques and technology well, to be able to analyze and innovate, to be knowledgeable and skillful. If the teacher is able to meaningfully

organize the lesson based on creativity, if he is able to use pedagogical technologies correctly and effectively, the interest of the student will increase.

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